

RES4LIVE

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

RES4LIVE promotional material

Deliverable 7.3

WP7. Dissemination – Communication – Exploitation

Project title

RES4LIVE - Energy Smart Livestock Farming towards Zero Fossil Fuel Consumption

Grant agreement: 101000785

From October 2020 to September 2024

Prepared by: CETRI

31/03/2021

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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

Deliverable no.	Deliverable 7.3: RES4LIVE promotional material
Responsible Partner	CETRI
WP no. and title	7. Dissemination – Communication – Exploitation
Task no. and title	7.1. Dissemination and communication plan and activities (M1-48, EUREC)
Version	1
Version Date	31/03/2021

Dissemination level	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU = Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

Approvals/ Document history

	Company/Institution
Author/s	CETRI
Task Leader	EUREC
WP Leader	CETRI

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ABBREVIATIONS

DCP: Dissemination and Communication Plan

KPI: Key Performance Indicator

PARTNERS SHORT NAMES

AUA - AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS

UNIBO – UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA

ATB - LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING AND BIOECONOMY

EV ILVO - RESEARCH INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURE, FISHERIES AND FOOD

UGENT - GHENT UNIVERSITY

CERTH - CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY-HELLAS

AU - AARHUS UNIVERSITY

LVAT - LEHR- UND VERSUCHSANSTALT FÜR TIERZUCHT UND TIERHALTUNG GROß KREUTZ E.V.

PSYCTOTHERM - G. LIGEROS & SIA OE

PLEGMA LABS- PLEGMA LABS TECHNOLOGIKES LYSEIS ANONYMOS ETAIRIA

CRMT SAS - CENTRE DE RECHERCHES EN MACHINES THERMIQUES

TERRA - TERRA ENERGY

MG SUSTAINABLE - MG SUSTAINABLE ENGINEERING AB

CETRI - CENTER FOR TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH & INNOVATION LTD

GOLINELLI - GOLINELLI GIULIO

EAAP - FEDERAZIONE EUROPEA PER LA ZOOTECNICA

EUREC - EUREC EESV

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The current document presents various promotional materials that will be used to disseminate activities carried out within the RES4LIVE project (Grant Agreement No. 101000785). The promotional materials are means to attract the interest of various stakeholders, such as: the general public, end-users and farmers' associations, policy makers, technology providers, universities and research centres, innovators, investors and other EU projects funded under the same Call. The goal of developing and distributing promotional materials is to make RES4LIVE widespread known in order to contribute in the further penetration of the use of Renewable Energy Sources in livestock farming, and facilitate the future exploitation of project results.

The structure of the document is as follows: the promotional materials that have already been developed are presented in Chapter 2.1, promotional materials that will be developed by the consortium in the future are included in Chapter 2.2, the way that the promotional materials have been taken into consideration in the Dissemination and Communication Plan is explained in Chapter 2.3, a short conclusion is included in Chapter 3 and the RES4LIVE logo manual can be found in Annex 1.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 7.3 RES4LIVE promotional material belongs to Work Package 7: Dissemination – Communication – Exploitation [Months: 1-48] and relates to Task 7.1: Dissemination and communication plan and activities (M1-48, EUREC). However, it should be noted that all WP7 Tasks will benefit from this Deliverable, as the work to be accomplished under Tasks 7.2 – 7.6 will heavily depend on the use of RES4LIVE’s promotional materials. The main objective of Deliverable 7.3 is to present in a coherent manner the promotional materials that the WP7 partners have already generated and shared in order to ensure high visibility and awareness on the project itself and its goals. The Deliverable also covers the consortium’s future plans on developing additional materials to keep disseminating and communicating the project’s progress, as the partners successfully reach their milestones. Lastly, the Deliverable touches upon the inclusion of the promotional materials in the RES4LIVE Dissemination and Communication Plan, thus, highlighting the importance of such materials and the impact that they could have in engaging with the project’s diverse target audience.

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2 PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

By promotional materials we will henceforth refer to all written, printed, graphic, electronic, audio or video presentations of information regarding the RES4LIVE project that are generated by the consortium to serve dissemination and communication purposes.

Nowadays, the use of promotional materials in physical and digital form has emerged as a very powerful dissemination and communication tool. It is of outmost importance to produce high-quality, comprehensive and capturing materials, which can even be customized according to the receiving audience.

The goal of the RES4LIVE promotional materials is to ensure widespread visibility on the project and engagement with a variety of interested stakeholders, including: the general public, end-users and farmers' associations, policy makers, technology providers, universities and research centres, innovators, investors and other EU projects funded under the same Call.

Building lines of communication and establishing relationships with all these parties could increase the public acceptance towards the use of Renewable Energy Sources in the field of livestock farming, inspire farmers alongside Europe to invest in more environmentally friendly practices and of course assist in the uptake of the RES4LIVE developed technologies by opening up various exploitation routes.

In Chapter 2.1 the promotional materials that have already been developed by WP7 partners are presented, while Chapter 2.2 includes the promotional materials that will be developed by the consortium in the future. Chapter 2.3 explains how the promotional materials have been taken into consideration in the Dissemination and Communication Plan. Chapter 3 drives a short conclusion based on the above.

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2.1 Promotional Materials already in use

The Table below summarizes the RES4LIVE promotional materials that the WP7 partners have developed so far. It should be noted that all materials in file formats with the following suffixes: ppt, doc, pdf, png, ai and gif are uploaded on RES4LIVE’s Intranet and Microsoft Teams for all partners to be able to access, download and use. Furthermore, all these promotional materials have already been used for dissemination and communication purposes via RES4LIVE’s website, social media accounts, YouTube account, event participations, clustering activities, emails, etc.

Table 1 RES4LIVE promotional Materials

RES4LIVE Promotional Materials
1. RES4LIVE Logo and Logo manual
2. RES4LIVE Public Deliverables (and Deliverable template)
3. RES4LIVE Newsletter
4. RES4LIVE Teaser video
5. RES4LIVE Brochure (leaflet)
6. RES4LIVE General presentation
7. RES4LIVE Presentation template
8. RES4LIVE Agenda template

Regarding the **RES4LIVE logo**, at the RES4LIVE Kick-off Meeting, EUREC presented to the consortium three candidate logo proposals and subsequently all partners were asked to express their preference via email. Once all partners had voted, EUREC shared with the rest of the consortium the final RES4LIVE logo, along with a detailed manual demonstrating how the logo should be used by all project partners. The logo manual can be found in Annex 1. Moreover, EUREC delivered the logo in different file formats, configurations and sizes to serve different purposes, for example they created the logo for the website thumbnail and the logo with no text for the Deliverables’ headers (see Figure below).

Figure 1: RES4LIVE logo for the website thumbnail (left) and RES4LIVE logo with no text (right)

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The project’s Public Deliverables can serve as promotional materials, especially within the scientific community. Therefore, EUREC developed a **RES4LIVE Deliverable template** to ensure that all project Deliverables will have homogenous format and aesthetics. Special care has been taken to ensure that the Deliverables’ text font and colours will match those used in RES4LIVE’s logo. Also, all **Public Deliverables** will be uploaded on RES4LIVE’s website to ensure that interested stakeholders will have free access and download rights.

Another RES4LIVE promotional material is the **RES4LIVE Newsletter**, which is planned to be issued by EAAP, once every six months. The Newsletter is in digital form and its purpose is to spread the project’s news to partners, stakeholders and other groups of interest. The Newsletter’s content is assembled by EAAP, while all partners are encouraged to participate and distribute the issues to their networks. The first Newsletter was issued in January 2021 and all relevant information has been reported in Deliverable 7.2. The cover page of the 1st Newsletter is depicted in the Figure below.

Figure 2: The cover page of the 1st Newsletter

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Moving on to the **RES4LIVE Teaser video**, it has been created by CETRI and uploaded on YouTube in a new RES4LIVE account. It is a 1 min and 46 seconds long animated video illustrating the RES4LIVE’s goal and main technologies. The scenario was written by CETRI, while all technical partners supported the video creation by sharing pictures of their respective technologies to accommodate the animation. The RES4LIVE video is available at this link: [RES4LIVE H2020 teaser video - YouTube](#), while the following Figure is a YouTube screenshot.

Figure 3: RES4LIVE Teaser video on YouTube

Next, CETRI also produced a **RES4LIVE Brochure (leaflet)** to be distributed at workshops and other events on agriculture, livestock farming and RES in different EU countries. As it can be seen in the following Figure, it is a 2-page brochure containing on the first page the project logo, infographics to present the basic project elements, the partners’ logos and all necessary EC credentials. The second page is dedicated to the project’s objectives and pillars.

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RES4LIVE
ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

The strategic objective of RES4LIVE is to develop and bring into the market integrated, cost-effective and case-sensitive RES solutions towards achieving fossil-free livestock farming.

17 Partners, 8 Countries, 48 Months, 5.8 M Budget

Objectives

The overall objective of RES4LIVE is to provide advanced and cost-effective technologies to the livestock sector that ensure the sustainability of the farms' operation, and the superior thermal comfort of the animals for increased productivity with minimum climate change impact.

The strategic objective is to develop and bring into the market integrated, cost-effective and case-sensitive RES solutions towards achieving fossil-free livestock farming. To that end, RES4LIVE will adapt and test promising RES technologies in energy-intensive livestock farming (swine, dairy and poultry) for greatly reducing the fossil energy that is the main source to cover the energy demand. Dedicated, optimal designs combined with energy efficiency and other solutions are proposed, demonstrated in 4 pilot farms and evaluated technically, economically, environmentally, and socially.

Pillars

RES4LIVE is articulated in the following 4 main Pillars:

- RES and machinery adaptation, and other technologies selection:** Adaptation of promising key RES technologies highly suitable for livestock farms, and machinery. Selection of commercial RES and energy efficiency technologies, solutions and measures that can be directly integrated in livestock farms.
- Pilot systems design, installation and testing:** RES-based energy systems and combined solutions will follow optimisation methodologies with smart energy control to conclude to their design, installation and eventually pilot testing in 4 selected farms of 3 different species. RES4LIVE emphasises on the long-term testing to confidently evaluate performance, indoor thermal comfort, durability, de-fossilising target set and end-user acceptance.
- Multi-level Assessment:** Assessment of the innovative RES-based systems applied on farms, in terms of technical, economic, social and environmental indicators.
- Replicability and impact generation:** RES4LIVE will implement case studies in a large variety of EU farms, and will cluster with relative projects and networks to achieve maximum stakeholders' engagement.

Follow us on social media #RES4LIVE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000785.

Figure 4: RES4LIVE Brochure (leaflet)

Moreover, in order to facilitate the partners' participation in events where they would represent RES4LIVE, EUREC developed a **RES4LIVE General presentation** in PowerPoint format. It is an eight-slide presentation which encompasses all basic project info, such as: logo, budget, partners, timeframe, technologies, pilot farms, pillars, website, social media, Newsletter, etc. A snapshot of the RES4LIVE General presentation is depicted in the following Figure. Another, **RES4LIVE Presentation template** was also put together by EUREC. This is essentially a plain PowerPoint template, which includes the project logo and other project credentials and is also set to the right colours and text font. The purpose of this empty template is to provide a canvas for the partners to build their own presentations.

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Figure 5: RES4LIVE General presentation

Lastly, a draft **RES4LIVE Agenda template** has been created by EUREC to support the consortium in the organization of events. The RES4LIVE project will organize three to four workshops and a final conference to disseminate its progress and findings. Among all organizational aspects, a nice and explicit agenda -that can also be shared online- is needed to attract the interest of several parties and expand the pool of event participants, invited speakers, etc. As supplementary materials, EUREC also prepared internal communication templates, such as meeting minutes templates, as well as, reporting templates to simplify administrative tasks related to the WP7.

2.2 Promotional Materials to be developed

Currently, RES4LIVE is at M6 and as the project progresses and tangible results are generated at the pilot farms, updated or new promotional materials should be developed. The promotional materials should always reflect the project's findings, successes and lesson learnt. The RES4LIVE consortium has already identified certain materials that should be developed in the future, including:

- A more **sophisticated and refined version of the RES4LIVE Brochure** (leaflet).
- **Promotional materials that will emerge from RES4LIVE's clustering activities** with other projects funded under FNR-06 A and B. A cluster has already been formed and the next Clustering meeting will take place on the 29th of April.
- The **RES4LIVE final video**, which will be also uploaded on RES4LIVE YouTube account and presented in Deliverable 7.6.
- The **RES4LIVE Best Practices handbook** (publicly available Deliverable 7.5 and free to download) presenting lessons learnt during the project, suggesting best practices and giving tips that will help achieve key structural and procedural reforms regarding the use of RES in the livestock sector.
- The **practice abstracts**: The agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI) has developed a common format for innovative projects to provide farmers, foresters, advisers or whoever is interested with short and concise practical information (so called 'practice

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abstracts'). The process of developing the abstracts will be documented in Deliverables 7.8 and 7.9.

2.3 Promotional Materials in the Dissemination and Communication Plan

A Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) has been built by EUREC defining the upcoming communication & dissemination activities. The effectiveness of the dissemination & communication activities will be monitored by periodically keeping score on our progress towards achieving the predefined communication and dissemination objectives.

With regards to the promotional materials, EUREC has actively included them in the DCP and has made sure that their use by the project partners is encouraged and monitored. First of all, EUREC created a **RES4LIVE Event reporting template** for all partners to document the details of the events that the plan to attend in order to promote and share their work conducted within RES4LIVE. As it can be seen in the following Figure -among other event information- the partners are also asked to report on the use of promotional materials that they made.

RES4LIVE external events dissemination reporting template						
Event	Title or name of the event Website if applicable			<input type="checkbox"/> Organized by third parties	Date	
				<input type="checkbox"/> Organized by RES4LIVE partner	Location	
Type of event	<input type="checkbox"/> Conference	<input type="checkbox"/> Seminar	<input type="checkbox"/> Workshop	<input type="checkbox"/> Exhibition / Fair	<input type="checkbox"/> Other:	<i>Indicate</i>
	<input type="checkbox"/> Showcase/Demo	<input type="checkbox"/> Meeting	<input type="checkbox"/> Forum	<input type="checkbox"/> Visit	<input type="checkbox"/> Campaign	
Description	Main focus, organizers, topics addressed, periodicity of celebration etc.				Associated costs:	<i>Inscription etc.</i>
RES4LIVE contribution	Presentation subject or name of the lecture, Purpose of RES4LIVE presentation, topics addressed, main contents of the presentation, partner contribution				Responsible partner:	
Audience	<input type="checkbox"/> Research/ Scientific community	<input type="checkbox"/> Industry ¹	<input type="checkbox"/> Customers (Farm owners, workers)	<input type="checkbox"/> Medias	<input type="checkbox"/> Other:	<i>Indicate</i>
	<input type="checkbox"/> Academics	<input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers/ authorities	<input type="checkbox"/> Civil Society	<input type="checkbox"/> Financial entities, investors	<input type="checkbox"/> Members of associations ² :	<i>Indicate which</i>
Attendants profiles:	Further specify if needed: i.e. Engineers, utilities, installers, promoters, manufacturers				Number of attendants:	
Feedback	Summarize the event, main reactions, interests from the audience and conclusions.					
Materials	Indicate the materials used or developed: power point presentation, leaflet, poster, video, Ad hoc Dossier, etc.					
Attachments	Indicate the information you send attached for the report: event agenda, photos, material specifically developed...etc. You can also include some pictures here.					

Figure 6: RES4LIVE Event reporting template

Furthermore, in the DCP, EUREC defined **scores or a Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** for the following promotional materials: Newsletters, Posters & flyers distributed or downloaded, Deliverables downloads, Video teaser views and Press releases. The following Table depicts the annual KPIs set in the DCP.

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Table 2: Dissemination and Communication Plan KPIs

ANNUAL KPIs			
Newsletters	2/ year	Number of opens: 5-22% = poor, 23%-50% = good, >50% = excellent	Annual new subscribers: <125 = poor, >125= good, > 125 = excellent
# Scientific publications		< 1 /year = poor, 1-2 = good, > 2 = excellent	
# Articles		<1 /year = poor, 1-2 = good, > 2 = excellent	
Events		KPI # of events presentations/ year: < 3 = poor, 3-5 = good, > 5 = excellent	# of stakeholders engaged /year: < 700 = poor, > 700-750 = good, > 750 = excellent
Posters & flyers distributed or downloaded		# of distributed/downloaded material: >250 = poor, 250-300 = good, > 300 = excellent	
Website visits		<3750 = poor, 3750-4000 = good; >4000 + = excellent	
*Deliverables downloads (during the project)		<100 downloads = poor, 100-200 = good; >200 = excellent	
Social media followers		< 200 = poor, 200-250 = good, > 250 = excellent	
# Press releases		1 per year minimum	

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3 CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, the RES4LIVE WP7 partners have developed several promotional materials, have already planned the development of new or enriched materials in the future and have given the materials proper attention by including them in the Dissemination and Communication Plan.

The RES4LIVE consortium aspires that the use of various materials in conjunction with events organization/participation, publications, social media activity, website content, clustering activities and other initiatives will allow them to follow the Dissemination and Communication Plan and create a strong network around RES4LIVE which will in turn ensure the sustainability of the project outcomes after its completion.

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Introduction

This document offers guidelines regarding the correct use of the RES4LIVE Logo

It is important that all elements of the guidelines are respected at all times

3

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

Composition

The logo is composed by the heart shaped symbol with coloured facets, accompanied by the text "RES4LIVE" and underlined by "ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION".

The logo/image can be used isolated or with the text as an entire entity.

The symbol has coloured facets, visualising the different sources and technologies. It is versatile and can be used to create icons and backgrounds in collateral material.

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ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

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Colours

The text accompanying the symbol is in shades of blue that appear in the symbol.

Blue
Light blue

BLUE	RED	23		CYAN	100
	GREEN	103		MAGENTA	51
	BLACK	175		YELLOW	0
				BLACK	0
LIGHT BLUE	RED	213		CYAN	20
	GREEN	220		MAGENTA	10
	BLACK	239		YELLOW	0
				BLACK	0

5

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

One colour

The logo should only be used in one colour (tints of grey) in case full colour is not possible.

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Bounding box

The bounding box guarantees a minimum of free space around the logo which needs to be respected at all times, apart for exceptions due to small space.

The logo should be positioned in the top right corner of all documents unless for technical or visual reasons, leaving a free space no smaller than equal to $1/2 x$.

- the height of the text = x
- the free border on all sides of the logo = $1/2 x$

7

Minimum size

The size of the logo for printed material shouldn't be less than 45 mm

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Typeface

The typeface used is Aglet Sans
For body text another typeface can be used.

Abc **Aglet Sans**
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz0123456789
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

9

UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA. CAMPUS BURJASSOT. AV. DEL NORD, 1065. BURJASSOT (VA) TEL: 963543000

Don'ts

- Do not deform the logo
- Do not rotate the logo
- Do not change the colour-way
- Always respect the white area
- Do not distort or italicise the logo
- Do not use shadow effects, embossing or any other effect on the logo
- Do not put the logo on a background
- Do not put elements within the bounding box, respect the free space
- Do not confine the logo within a shape

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Contact

If you require logos, material or any further assistance, please contact:

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